

From the Syllabus towards Vatican II:

The increase of Human Rights Discourse as an indicator of a
Natural Law Knowledge Base Shift

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Introduction

In 1864 Pope Pius IX (d. 1878) published two encyclicals, *Quanta Cura* (QC) and *Syllabus Errorum* (SE).¹ QC focused on the relation of church and state and freedom of religion, while SE is a list of errors adding more subjects concerning philosophical concepts as pantheism. In QC, Pope Pius IX calls the idea of freedom of religion an "insanity".² Several of the errors recorded in the SE also reject the idea of freedom of religion:

- I. "Every man is free to embrace and profess that religion which, guided by the light of reason, he shall consider true."
- II. "In the present day it is no longer expedient that the Catholic religion should be held as the only religion of the State, to the exclusion of all other forms of worship."
- III. "Hence it has been wisely decided by law, in some Catholic countries, that persons coming to reside therein shall enjoy the public exercise of their own peculiar worship."
- IV. "Moreover, it is false that the civil liberty of every form of worship, and the full power, given to all, of overtly and publicly manifesting any opinions whatsoever and thoughts, conduce more easily to corrupt the morals and minds of the people, and to propagate the pest of indifferentism."³

¹ *Quanta Cura (Condemning Current Errors)*, accessed 18 June 2015, <http://www.ewtn.com/library/ENCYC/P9QUANTA.HTM>. *Syllabus Errorum (Syllabus of Errors)*, accessed 18 June 2015, <http://www.ewtn.com/library/PAPALDOC/P9SYLL.HTM>.

² *Quanta Cura*, article 3.

³ *Syllabus*, articles 15, 77, 78, and 79 respectively.

Exactly a hundred and one year later in 1965 Pope Paul VI (d. 1978) signed the declaration on religious freedom, *Dignitatis Humanae*⁴, formulated by the Vatican II council, which states:

- I. "Religious communities also have the right not to be hindered in their public teaching and witness to their faith, whether by the spoken or by the written word."
- II. "The family, since it is a society in its own original right, has the right freely to live its own domestic religious life under the guidance of parents. Parents, moreover, have the right to determine, in accordance with their own religious beliefs, the kind of religious education that their children are to receive."
- III. "It follows that a wrong is done when government imposes upon its people, by force or fear or other means, the profession or repudiation of any religion, or when it hinders men from joining or leaving a religious community."
- IV. "God calls men to serve Him in spirit and in truth, hence they are bound in conscience but they stand under no compulsion. God has regard for the dignity of the human person whom He Himself created and man is to be guided by his own judgment and he is to enjoy freedom."⁵

Similar conflicts are seen on the subjects of democracy⁶ and non-catholic salvation.⁷ Also

Pope Pius X (d. 1914)'s Encyclical rejection of modern studies on Biblical criticism and the

⁴ *Declaration on Religious Freedom - Dignitatis Humanae*, accessed 21 June 2015, http://www.vatican.va/archive/hist_councils/ii_vatican_council/documents/vat-ii_decl_19651207_dignitatis-humanae_en.html

⁵ *Dignitatis Humanae*, articles 4, 5, 6, and 11 respectively.

⁶ Kurt Martens. 'Dignitatis Humanae: A Hermeneutic Perspective on Religious Freedom as Interpreted by the Roman Catholic Church'. In *Hermeneutics, Scriptural Politics, and Human Rights: Between Text and Context*, edited by Bas Gaay de Fortman, Kurt Martens, and M. A. Mohamed Salih (New York: Palgrave MacMillan, 2009), 150-151.

⁷ See the *Nostra Aetate* articles in the appendix attached to this paper together with the QC, SE and DH articles.

evolutionary history of dogma⁸, was formulated into an '*oath against modernism*' which rejected any concept of the evolution of dogma or the agnostic scientific stance on church history and the Bible.⁹ Every church official involved with the Vatican II decrees and declarations has sworn that oath, while the Vatican II stances clearly do accept evolutionary changes of dogma¹⁰ and the scientific study of the Bible.¹¹ For many Catholics these conflicts were obvious and have created several responses which can be classified in two main hermeneutical approaches:

- **Hermeneutics of Continuity:** All declarations claim that religious truth is found in and through the Church, and that the assumed differences are a misunderstanding of the pastoral organic approach to the tradition. Some of them call for a "Syllabus of Errors" of wrong liberal interpretations of Vatican II.¹² Thus Vatican II is a pastoral approach to the world and Church tradition and does not represent any major shift.

⁸ *Pascendi Dominici Gregis (On the Doctrines of the Modernists)*, accessed 18 June 2015, http://w2.vatican.va/content/pius-x/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_p-x_enc_19070908_pascendi-dominici-gregis.html.

⁹ *The Oath against Modernism*, accessed 21 June 2015, <http://www.papalencyclicals.net/Pius10/p10moath.htm>.

¹⁰ The acceptance of non-Catholic salvation in *Nostra Aetate* clearly goes against the dogmatic declaration of the Council of Trent (1546), see an important discussion on this in: Jeannine Hill Fletcher, 'Responding to Religious Difference: Conciliar Perspectives', in *From Trent to Vatican II: Historical and Theological Investigations*, edited by Raymond Bulman and Frederick J. Parrella (New York: Oxford University Press, 2006), 267-271.

¹¹ See the '*Constitution on Divine Revelation (Dei Verbum)*', and the discussion on it in Walter M. Abbot, and Joseph Gallagher, eds. *The Documents of Vatican II With Notes and Comments by Catholic, Protestant, and Orthodox Authorities* (USA: The American Press, 1966), 107-132.

¹² Interestingly enough, Pope Benedict XVI has called for such a Syllabus and rejects the idea of a hermeneutics of discontinuity, while at the same time acknowledging that the Vatican II declarations and decrees represent a "countersyllabus". See: Pope Benedict XVI, 'A Proper Hermeneutic for the Second Vatican Council'. In *Vatican II Renewal within Tradition*, edited by Matthew L. Lamb and Matthew Levering (New York: Oxford University Press, 2008), ix-xv. And: Martens, *Ibid*, 151.

- **Hermeneutics of Discontinuity:**

A. **Schism view:** Vatican II is a schismatic rupture with the original teachings of the popes preceding John XXIII, making him and Paul VI heretics. The Traditionalists (with the Pius X society as the most extreme) claim that the changes in liturgy, the relativizing of the truth and salvation in the Church, the call for religious and political liberty, the acknowledgement of Modernism and Liberalism, the positive view on other religions, and the positive view on mankind ignoring Original Sin, are all major heresies for which Pius IX and X warned against. Thus Vatican II is a schismatic heretical shift.¹³

B. **Progressive view:** The Church acknowledges its hermeneutical position towards the truth in ritualistic, moral and religious sense by saying that the true church subsists in the Church, that religious and political liberty is part of Natural law, acknowledging the presence of truth and shared similarities in other religions, and people from other religions with goodwill as a form of "anonymous Christians". Thus Vatican II is a positive paradigm shift.¹⁴

To understand which hermeneutic of Vatican II portrays the changes in a better light, I want to propose to not only look at the Vatican II texts themselves compared to their predecessors, but also to look at the contextual and epistemological changes that occurred between 1864 and

¹³ See for example: the Society of St. Pius X, District of Asia, *The Errors of Vatican II*, accessed on 21 June 2015, http://www.sspxasia.com/Documents/SiSiNoNo/2003_January/errors_of_vatican_II.htm. And Traditional Catholics which are anti-Vatican II: Most Holy Family Monastery, *The Vatican II Revolution (1962-1965)*, accessed on 21 June 2015, http://www.mostholyfamilymonastery.com/8_VaticanII.pdf. For an overview of the schism view, see: Massimo Faggioli, *Vatican II: The Battle for Meaning* (New Jersey: Paulist Press, 2012), 438-522.

¹⁴ Important Vatican II theologians representing the progressive view are Edward Schillebeeckx (d. 2009), Hans Küng, Yves Congar (d. 1995), and Karl Rahner (d. 1984), see: Faggioli, *Ibid*, 389.

1965. These changes caused, what Bernie Koenig calls, *Knowledge Base Shifts* within theological Natural Law. As Natural Law theory is based on the concept of a natural order of things, when this concept of that order changes, so do the Natural Law stances.¹⁵ As Natural Law theory is central to Catholic theology, a slow or fast change will occur within its theology, depending on how it views the epistemological and contextual changes.

Examples of Knowledge Base Shifts in Catholic Natural Law Theology

Examples of these Knowledge Base Shifts can be seen in how the Catholic Church viewed the relation between Church and state and the rights of citizens as expressed in freedom of religion. QC and SE reject freedom of religion as this freedom was viewed as being closely linked to the French Revolution and the foundation of the secular state through "popular rule" (i.e. democracy)¹⁶, and the founding of the Italian state which had taken much territory from the Papal states.¹⁷ But the popes after Pius IX slowly adopted human rights discourse into their writings and speeches. To see this Knowledge Base Shift we shall view them in order:

- I. *Quanta Cura* and *Syllabus Errorum* (1864, Pius IX): Display of false opinions of modernity as freedom of religion. Considered a late reaction against the French Revolution, and contemporary reaction against a united Italian state.
- II. Vatican Council (1869-1870, Pius IX) : Claims jurisdiction over the whole Church against civil liberties, as a response to European governments claiming power over local churches

¹⁵ Bernie Koenig, *Natural Law, Science, And the Social Construction of Reality* (Maryland: University Press of America, 2004), 299-301.

¹⁶ Martens, *Ibid*, 147-150.

¹⁷ Diarmaid MacCulloch, *A History of Christianity* (UK: Penguin Books, 2009), 821.

offices and properties. Several bishops broke away from the Church to join the Old Catholic Church (Union of Utrecht) over Vatican I's Papal infallibility.¹⁸

III. *Immortale Dei* (1885, Leo XIII): The Church respects civil government and doesn't reject any form of government as long it pursues the common good. God has charged mankind with two powers, the ecclesiastical and the civil. Law must not be based on the caprices of the masses, but on Natural Law, so that no conflict arises between the two powers.¹⁹

IV. *Libertas* (1888, Leo XIII): Acknowledges liberty as Natural law but only good when guided by the Church, rejects secular government as only a religious government can acknowledge Natural law and thus Natural rights.²⁰

V. *Rerum Novarum* (1891, Leo XIII): Against Socialism, but is for unions and labor rights with the Church as mediator against abuse of the laborer by the ones who control capital.²¹

VI. *Graves de Communi Re* (1901, Leo XIII): On the development of the Christian democracy movement as response to social democracy, whereby the intention of the movement is respected, but is rebuked for applying the Church into party politics. Law is based on nature and the Gospel and not on popular rule.²²

¹⁸ MacCulloch, *Ibid*, 824-825.

¹⁹ *Immortale Dei (On the Christian Constitution of States)*, accessed 21 June 2015, http://w2.vatican.va/content/leo-xiii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_l-xiii_enc_01111885_immortale-dei.html.

²⁰ *Libertas (On the Nature of Human Liberty)*, accessed 17 June 2015, http://w2.vatican.va/content/leo-xiii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_l-xiii_enc_20061888_libertas.html.

²¹ *Rerum Novarum (On Capital and Labor)*, accessed 17 June 2015, http://w2.vatican.va/content/leo-xiii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_l-xiii_enc_15051891_rerum-novarum.html.

²² *Graves de Communi Re (On Christian Democracy)*, accessed 17 June 2015, http://w2.vatican.va/content/leo-xiii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_l-xiii_enc_18011901_graves-de-communi-re.html.

VII. *Pascendi Dominici Gregeris* (1907, Pius X): Against Modernistic trends whereby science is placed above faith, and the belief in evolutionary progress of doctrines and the claims made by Biblical criticism, as this goes counter to Natural Law as expressed in Pius X's Neo-Thomism.

VIII. Christmas radio messages to the world (1942/44, Pius XII): Use of *dignità umana* in relation to human rights and a just government as a response to fascism and WWII.²³

IX. *Communium Interpretes Dolorum* (1944, Pius XII): War goes against divine and human rights.²⁴

X. *Ad Petri Cathedram* (1959, John XXIII): First apostolic writing using modern human rights discourse as the inviolability of rights and liberty as pre-political rights.²⁵

XI. *Mater Et Magistra* (1961, John XXIII): Overview of the development of labor rights in Papal statements from *Rerum Novarum* up to his time.²⁶

XII. *Pacem in Terris* (1963, John XXIII): First apostolic writing following and acknowledging the human rights articles as drafted in the UNDHR: natural rights as human rights, freedom within moral limits, freedom of religion, individual rights in

²³ *Con Sempre Nuova Freschezza” - Il Santo Natale E L’umanità Dolorante (Christmas Radio Message La Umanita Dolerante (The Aching Humanity))*, accessed 18 June 2015, http://w2.vatican.va/content/pius-xii/it/speeches/1942/documents/hf_p-xii_spe_19421224_radiomessage-christmas.html. *Radiomessaggio Natalizio Ai Popoli Del Amondo Intero, 24 Dicembre 1944 - Pio XII, Discorsi (Christmas Radio Message Benignitas et Humanitas (Goodness and Human Kindness))*, accessed 18 June 2015, http://www.vatican.va/holy_father/pius_xii/speeches/1944/documents/hf_p-xii_spe_19441224_natale_it.html.

²⁴ *Communium Interpretes Dolorum (Appealing for Prayers for Peace during May)*, accessed 21 June 2015, http://w2.vatican.va/content/pius-xii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_p-xii_enc_15041945_communium-interpretis-dolorum.html.

²⁵ *Ad Petri Cathedram (On Truth, Unity and Peace)*, accessed 21 June 2015, http://w2.vatican.va/content/john-xxiii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_j-xxiii_enc_29061959_ad-petri.html.

²⁶ *Mater Et Magistra (On Christianity and Social Progress)*, accessed on 21 June 2015, http://w2.vatican.va/content/john-xxiii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_j-xxiii_enc_15051961_mater.html.

relation to society and government, coercion is against common good, state has no power of men's conscience unless it's tied to God's authority by following Natural law, government is to safeguard rights & duties of men, people are free to worship according to their own conscience.²⁷

XIII. Second Vatican Council (1963-65, John XXIII, Paul VI): 4 constitutions (on dogma of church and scripture, church in the modern world, and on liturgy), nine decrees (on missionary, training priests, Oriental churches, religious life, clergy life, ecumenism), and three declarations (religious liberty, Christian education, and relations with other religions). Several cardinals, bishops and parishes broke away from the Church, calling Vatican II a heresy.

From Pius IX to Pius X, the Vatican state had lost its territory completely, and saw its influences being reduced by secular civil nationalistic governments or empires. This loss was blamed on Enlightenment ideals of the supremacy of reason and social contract theory, and as such these ideals were attacked or tried to be frameworked into a Catholic Natural Law ethics. We see this frameworking especially with Leo XIII who in the process slowly adopts human rights discourse. During WWII we see Pius XII for the first time applying the term human dignity in relation to human rights, but during his long pontificate (1939-1958) we see human rights discourse minimally present in his writings.²⁸ Still we see important Knowledge Base

²⁷ *Pacem in Terris* (April, 11 1963), accessed 21 June 2015, http://w2.vatican.va/content/john-xxiii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_j-xxiii_enc_11041963_pacem.html. Even with *Pacem in Terris*, Vatican II and the popes afterwards acknowledging modern human rights, the Vatican as a (non-UN observer status) state still hasn't signed the 1948 UDHR or the 1966/1997 ICCPR, but has endorsed and supported them and other HR declarations in the UNHRC. Thus it supports it as a moral force, not as a temporal force.

²⁸ For example in his Encyclical on the Church in China, the term "rights" is applied four times for the "rights of the church", and only once for the "rights of the human person" against persecution. *Ad Apostolorum Principis (On Communism and the Church in China)*. Accessed on 21 June 2015. http://w2.vatican.va/content/pius-xii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_p-xii_enc_29061958_ad-apostolorum-principis.html.

Shifts that have occurred, whereby we went from the vision of the state and Church working in unison to the state being a threat to religion. The first response was fighting religious freedom as the source of the loss of power towards accepting religious freedom as a way to exist under suppressive or totalitarian rule. After both world wars and the communist revolution, the world had completely changed, and so had the Church. Even though Pius XII rarely discussed human rights, many important Church officials and theologians were central in the establishment of the post-World Wars' human rights regime. Jacques Maritain (d. 1973), a French Thomist philosopher, publishes several important works in the 1930's and 40's, of which the *The Rights of Man and Natural Law* (1942) is the most influential in Catholic circles.²⁹ Maritain was close friends to both the Apostolic Nuncio Roncalli and Curia official Montini, the later popes John XXIII (d. 1963) and Paul VI, and was chosen as the French ambassador to Vatican city in 1944.³⁰ John XXIII urges Maritain to develop an international human rights scheme, which laid the foundation of the United Nations Declaration of Human Rights (UNDHR) in 1948.³¹ In his works, Maritain reconciled Enlightenment human rights discourse, democracy, and religious pluralism³² with Thomistic Natural Law.³³ After John XXIII was elected pope, in his first Encyclical *Ad Petri Cathedram* he focused on the concept of inviolability of rights and liberty as a form of pre-political rights applying Maritain's rights

²⁹ Catherine M.A. McCauliff, 'Jacques Maritain's Embrace of Religious Pluralism and the Declaration on Religious Freedom', *Seton Hall Law Review* 41 (19 April 2011): 593.

³⁰ Catherine M.A. McCauliff, *The Friendship of Pope Paul VI and Jacques Maritain and the Declaration on Religious Freedom*, accessed on 18 June 2015, http://works.bepress.com/catherine_mc_cauliff/1, 1-6.

³¹ Jacques Maritain, *Natural Law: Reflections on Theory and Practice* (South Bend, IN: St. Augustine's Press, 2001), 6.

³² For an important discussion on this shift in Natural Law theology, see: Robert P. George, 'Natural Law and Human Rights: A Conversation'. In *Does Human Rights Need God?*, edited by Elizabeth M. Bucar and Barbra Barnett (Cambridge: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 2005), 135-144.

³³ Carrie Rose Stibora, *Jacques Maritain and Alasdair MacIntyre on Human Rights* (PhD Thesis, The Catholic University of America. Washington, 2013), 38-39. McCauliff, *Jacques Maritain's Embrace*, 598-601.

discourse. In his last Encyclical *Pacem in Terris* he even applied the order of the UNDHR articles, thereby giving a papal acknowledgement and approval of the UNDHR. The Vatican II declaration on religious freedom (*Dignitatis Humanae*) verbally cites parts from Maritain's writings³⁴, showing his overall influence on the bishops whom directly steered the council away from the Roman Curia's original conservative agenda and proposals for the council.³⁵ The human rights Knowledge Base Shift which was present in the mindset among the majority of the bishops influenced even the constitution on the Church (*Lumen Gentium*) which had restructured the classical pyramid Church hierarchy with the pope on top, into a circle of functions which emphasized the equality of all baptized, and in the constitution on liturgy (*Sacrosanctum Concilium*) which included the laity as fellow performers of the liturgy in such a way that the majority of altars in Catholic churches were turned around from God to face the church community.³⁶ Democracy, human rights, freedom of religion, religious pluralism, had all become part of Catholic Natural Law theology due to Knowledge Base Shifts of war, religious and ethnic persecution, and totalitarianism.

Conclusion

After our review of the shifts from the *Syllabus* towards Vatican II, we can thus conclude there is both a hermeneutic of continuity and discontinuity, as Vatican II didn't depart from Thomism, but reviewed it based on shifts in the way it understood the order of things. The

³⁴ McCauliff, *Jacques Maritain's Embrace*, 602-612.

³⁵ M. J. Wilde, K. Geraty, S. L. Nelson, and E. A. Bowman, 'Religious Economy or Organizational Field?: Predicting Bishops' Votes at the Second Vatican Council', *American Sociological Review* 75, no. 4 (2010): 586–606.

³⁶ Abbott, *Ibid*, 92-105, 133-181.

reshuffling of the world not simply changed the borders of countries, but the whole way the human views itself in the world. As the human has taken a new position, so does the way it views the world, and even God.³⁷ It was thus inevitable that this would affect the Church somehow, and it was the insight of John XXIII that a council of global bishops could shift the Church itself. Human rights discourse has become part and parcel of Catholic thought³⁸ in a way that would have been inconceivable for Pius IX, as his Knowledge Base Stance would not have allowed it to understand it. The opponents of Vatican II who view it as a schism thus seemingly try to live in a pre-1900 world mindset, which logically can never gain any large following, as for the majority of mankind the order of things has shifted towards the *humanum* being expressed and encapsulated by human rights discourse. The progressive theologians of Vatican II hoped the council would also change its stances on anti-conception, celibacy, homosexuality and women's ordination, but for that, a new trickling down (or up?) of contemporary Knowledge Base Stances is needed. Many hope that Pope Francis will change the Church on these matters³⁹, but it would be better to believe that another future synod or council will eventually take the Knowledge Base Shifts which are already widespread within mankind.

³⁷ For an ingenious discussion on this, see: Martin Palouš, 'What Kind of God Does Human Rights Require?' In *Does Human Rights Need God?*, edited by Elizabeth M. Bucar and Barbra Barnett (Cambridge: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 2005), 243-268.

³⁸ David Hollenbach, 'Human Rights in a Pluralist, Unequal Globe: Contributions of Jesuit Universities'. *Catholic Education: A Journal of Inquiry and Practice* 14, no. 3 (March 2011), 338-343.

³⁹ As with his worldwide questionnaire which resulted in the 2015 Family Synod.

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Vatican Encyclicals, Declarations and other Messages:

Pope Pius IX:

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1864 *Syllabus Errorum (Syllabus of Errors)*. Accessed 18 June 2015. <http://www.ewtn.com/library/PAPALDOC/P9SYLL.HTM>.

Leo XIII:

1885 *Immortale Dei (On the Christian Constitution of States)*. Accessed 21 June 2015. http://w2.vatican.va/content/leo-xiii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_l-xiii_enc_01111885_immortale-dei.html.

1888 *Libertas (On the Nature of Human Liberty)*. Accessed 17 June 2015. http://w2.vatican.va/content/leo-xiii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_l-xiii_enc_20061888_libertas.html.

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1901 *Graves de Communi Re (On Christian Democracy)*. Accessed 17 June 2015. http://w2.vatican.va/content/leo-xiii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_l-xiii_enc_18011901_graves-de-communi-re.html.

Pope Pius X:

1907 *Pascendi Dominici Gregis (On the Doctrines of the Modernists)*. Accessed 18 June 2015. http://w2.vatican.va/content/pius-x/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_p-x_enc_19070908_pascendi-dominici-gregis.html.

1910 *The Oath against Modernism*. Accessed 21 June 2015. <http://www.papalencyclicals.net/Pius10/p10moath.htm>.

Pope Pius XII:

1942 *Con Sempre Nuova Freschezza” - Il Santo Natale E L’umanità Dolorante (Christmas Radio Message La Umanita Dolerante (The Aching Humanity))*. Accessed 18 June 2015. http://w2.vatican.va/content/pius-xii/it/speeches/1942/documents/hf_p-xii_spe_19421224_radiomessage-christmas.html.

1944 *Radiomessaggio Natalizio Ai Popoli Del Amondo Intero, 24 Dicembre 1944 - Pio XII, Discorsi (Christmas Radio Message Benignitas et Humanitas (Goodness and Human Kindness))*. Accessed 18 June 2015. http://www.vatican.va/holy_father/pius_xii/speeches/1944/documents/hf_p-xii_spe_19441224_natale_it.html.

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John XXIII:

1959 *Ad Petri Cathedram (On Truth, Unity and Peace)*. Accessed 21 June 2015. http://w2.vatican.va/content/john-xxiii/en/encyclicals/documents/hf_j-xxiii_enc_29061959_ad-petri.html.

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Appendix: Side by side overview of the Syllabus Errorum, Quanta Cura, Dignitatis Humanae and Nostra Aetate⁴⁰

Contradictions between the texts?	
Syllabus Errorum (These statements are deemed as false)	<p>"Every man is free to embrace and profess that religion which, guided by the light of reason, he shall consider true." (SE 15)</p> <p>"Man may, in the observance of any religion whatever, find the way of eternal salvation, and arrive at eternal salvation.—Encyclical "Qui pluribus," Nov. 9, 1846." (SE 16)</p> <p>"Good hope at least is to be entertained of the eternal salvation of all those who are not at all in the true Church of Christ.—Encyclical "Quanto conficiamur," Aug. 10, 1863, etc." (SE 17)</p> <p>"In the present day it is no longer expedient that the Catholic religion should be held as the only religion of the State, to the exclusion of all other forms of worship." (SE 77)</p> <p>"Hence it has been wisely decided by law, in some Catholic countries, that persons coming to reside therein shall enjoy the public exercise of their own peculiar worship." (SE 78)</p> <p>"Moreover, it is false that the civil liberty of every form of worship, and the full power, given to all, of overtly and publicly manifesting any opinions whatsoever and thoughts, conduce more easily to corrupt the morals and minds of the people, and to propagate the pest of indifferentism." (SE 79)</p>
Quanta Cura	<p>"From which totally false idea of social government they do not fear to foster that erroneous opinion, most fatal in its effects on the Catholic Church and the salvation of souls, called by Our Predecessor, Gregory XVI, an "insanity,"² viz., that "liberty of conscience and worship is each man's personal right, which ought to be legally proclaimed and asserted in every rightly constituted society; and that a right resides in the citizens to an absolute liberty, which should be restrained by no authority whether ecclesiastical or civil, whereby they may be able openly and publicly to manifest and declare any of their ideas whatever, either by word of mouth, by the press, or in any other way." (QC 3)</p>

⁴⁰ To avoid excessive footnotes the sources will be mentioned in brackets; Syllabus Errorum (SE), Quanta Cura (QC), Dignitatis Humanae (DH), Nostra Aetate (NA).

Contradictions between the texts?	
Dignitatis Humanae	<p>"A sense of the dignity of the human person has been impressing itself more and more deeply on the consciousness of contemporary man,(1) and the demand is increasingly made that men should act on their own judgment, enjoying and making use of a responsible freedom." (DH 1)</p> <p>"Religious communities also have the right not to be hindered in their public teaching and witness to their faith, whether by the spoken or by the written word." (DH 4)</p> <p>"The family, since it is a society in its own original right, has the right freely to live its own domestic religious life under the guidance of parents. Parents, moreover, have the right to determine, in accordance with their own religious beliefs, the kind of religious education that their children are to receive." (DH 5)</p> <p>"It follows that a wrong is done when government imposes upon its people, by force or fear or other means, the profession or repudiation of any religion, or when it hinders men from joining or leaving a religious community." (DH 6)</p> <p>"God calls men to serve Him in spirit and in truth, hence they are bound in conscience but they stand under no compulsion. God has regard for the dignity of the human person whom He Himself created and man is to be guided by his own judgment and he is to enjoy freedom." (DH. 11)</p>
Nostra Aetate	<p>"The Catholic Church rejects nothing that is true and holy in these religions. She regards with sincere reverence those ways of conduct and of life, those precepts and teachings which, though differing in many aspects from the ones she holds and sets forth, nonetheless often reflect a ray of that Truth which enlightens all men. Indeed, she proclaims, and ever must proclaim Christ "the way, the truth, and the life" (John 14:6), in whom men may find the fullness of religious life, in whom God has reconciled all things to Himself." (NA 2)</p> <p>"The Church regards with esteem also the Moslems. They adore the one God, living and subsisting in Himself; merciful and all- powerful, the Creator of heaven and earth,(5) who has spoken to men; they take pains to submit wholeheartedly to even His inscrutable decrees, just as Abraham, with whom the faith of Islam takes pleasure in linking itself, submitted to God." (NA 3)</p> <p>"True, the Jewish authorities and those who followed their lead pressed for the death of Christ;(13) still, what happened in His passion cannot be charged against all the Jews, without distinction, then alive, nor against the Jews of today. Although the Church is the new people of God, the Jews should not be presented as rejected or accursed by God." (NA 4)</p>